

Artificial Intelligence for Space Operations (AI) (13)
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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR SATCOM OPERATIONS

Abstract

¹Artificial Intelligence (AI) might become a crucial element for satellite communications (SATCOM) operations. Procedures based on AI techniques are meant to reduce the human intervention in all space operations value chain and, consequently, reduce the operational expenditures of the overall satellite systems. Remarkably, the rolling out of the mentioned AI novel procedures would require a deep revisit of current approaches. In this contribution we identify some of the SATCOM operations that might be enhanced by the usage of AI mechanisms. The first use case is the development of machine learning techniques to discover anomaly events in the telemetry data. Satellite on board parameters are controlled by the teleport or control system via checking its maximum and minimum values so as its derivative progression. This out-of-limits approach presents a high time-to-react so that the system can only actuate whenever the event has already occurred. This prevents an efficient control system. The conceived technique aims to detect hidden patterns of the data which will alert of system anomalies despite the considered parameters are under their permitted value limits. The AI model able to capture the mentioned operation is anomaly detection in time series. This well-known technique is divided in two main approaches; namely, reconstruction or distance based. Notice how this use case is not specific to SATCOM but applicable to any satellite mission.

Unfortunately, interferences in satellite communications are usually frequent. Due to the broadcast propagation, interferences may come from other satellites, terrestrial base stations or amateur operations, among others. Currently, the only way to detect interference is by an experienced person inspecting figures such as the spectrum. Here we propose an automated system capable of interference detection. We propose the use of autoencoder Deep Neural Networks (DNN-AE) techniques in order to identify the presence of interferences. As a major gain, we expect to reduce the signal-to-interference ratio capable maintaining the accuracy. This will allow the detection of low-powered interferences and increase the confidence of the overall system. Moreover, since the system will be unattended, the costs will be reduced and the time of reaction will be improved, since all of manual tasks related with interference identification will be automated.

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As explained in the previous case, interference management is a critical task in satellite communications. If it is not performed carefully, it may degrade the quality of the service. Having information about the interferences as much as possible helps to delimitate their origin and may help to satellite operators to take decisions. Here we propose an interference classifier able to identify and classify which waveform is interfering. In other words, the classificatory shall be able to identify which standard follows the interference (5G-NR, LTE, UMTS, etc.). Recurrent deep neural networks are specially indicated for temporal signals. Furthermore, they are able to perform predictions and label the inputs based on the trained data. In our case, we can exploit this feature to identify which kind of signal is interfering. In satellite networks, the user distributions are unbalanced due to the geography and the population dispersion. As a result, some satellites have few traffic loads, while others have heavy traffic loads, which often lead to congestion events. We propose a machine learning-based method that predicts network loads and detects congested areas before they actually experience congestion. The user congestion prediction exploits the unsupervised classification of users according to their traffic profile and enables the load prediction.

In forthcoming flexible payloads, the available bandwidth and power is meant to be adapted in very short time periods with the aim of providing to the user terminals the requested services. In this context, it will be easy for the operator to react to interference events where certain beams are damaged by unintentional signals. Note that these events are expected to increase in the coming years as part of the Ka band will be occupied by 5G networks. The goal here is to develop a mechanism able to provide flexible payload optimization in terms of power allocation per feed element, bandwidth allocation and beamforming design, given a sudden change in the interference power level of a certain coverage area. The new payload configuration shall be provided in a short time lapse and; thus, the mechanism shall present a reduced computational complexity. The AI model for this use case focuses on training a feedforward network given a training set of inputs-output of known flexible payload optimizer.